

Supplemental Fig. S2

Supplemental Fig. S2 (related to **Materials and Methods**). **Quantitative measurement of tissue size via stereomicroscopy.** The human liver specimen was first immersed in PBS (between coverslips) and then imaged via stereomicroscopy (Carl Zeiss, SteREO Discovery.V12) to record the pixels occupied by the tissue (defined as 100). Afterward, the tissue was cleared in the A-ha copolymer (or clearing liquid, **Fig. 1J-M**) and then imaged again under the same microscope. The number of pixels recorded in the clearing condition was divided by that in PBS to estimate the relative tissue size after optical clearing (y axis of **Fig. 1N**). In the process, the same background “Human liver” was placed under the specimen to serve as the size standard (relative to tissue) and to demonstrate the change in tissue transparency.